

Family and Incest in Isaac Bashevis Singer's novel *Shadows on the Hudson*

Dr. Deepak Kishanrao Nagarkar

Assistant Professor in English

Venutai Chavan College, Karad

Corresponding Author – Dr. Deepak Kishanrao Nagarkar

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.20592001

Abstract:

The novels by Isaac Bashevis Singer portray protagonists that are trapped in incest and adultery not by will but by chance. They enjoy women to such an extent where they realize, the more they run after flesh, the more they get frustrated. The thought that they are committing a sin comes by reading of the scriptures that they are well aware of. The protagonists want to escape the trap for which they have to give up everything and accept God as their only saviour. This paper is about one such protagonist whose life struggle makes us aware of our family and our responsibility towards it.

Keywords: Renunciation, Fate, Responsibility, Family, Incest, God.

Isaac Bashevis Singer was a Jewish novelist born in Leoncin village near Warsaw, Poland on 11 November 1903. In 1935, Singer emigrated from Poland to the United States of America. He wrote around 18 novels and more than 150 short stories. He published his work in Yiddish and later translated his own works into English with the help of editors and collaborators. He was awarded Nobel Prize in Literature in 1978. His novel *Shadows on the Hudson* was published in 1998 after his death on 24 July 1991. The novel is set in New York. Boris Makaver is a businessman settled in New York from Warsaw who invites his Jew acquaintances at his house for dinner on Jewish festive days. His wife died in Warsaw twenty-three years ago. His daughter Anna is married a second time with Stanslaw Luria. Anna was first married to a Galician Comedian Yasha Kotik which lasted not more than a year. Among the guests, there is Hertz Grein who can be called the protagonist of the novel. He is about forty-five and has a wife and two children but he never takes his family to public occasions. In the house of her father, Anna

makes open advancements towards Grein. Boris has known Grein many years. Grein was close to Boris's wife and his daughter also. When Anna and Luria get up to go, Boris requests Grein to drop them. When they reach the house, Luria requests Grein to have a cup of coffee with them. After some time, Anna starts quarrel with her husband Luria and asks Grein to see her off at her father's house. Grein was waiting for this moment when he could spend some time privately with Anna but he could not confess it openly. They spent that night together in a hotel.

Grein goes to his house to tell Leah that he is going with Anna but when he reaches home she is not there. She has opened an antiques shop where she spends most of her time. His daughter Anita is in her room. Even after calling her name repeatedly, she does not answer. His son Jack is a licensed Engineer but he never works. He is after girls and comes home as if it is a hotel. Jack and Anita are not in good terms with their father. He is just a facilitator for them. Grein's wife Leah was happy with Grein but when he started having affairs with other women, she took on with her

own business. The family is in a mess and Grein is not wanted in it. The four of them live in a house but none is happy. Grein is exhausted with his stay in the hotel with Anna. He wants rest. Early in the morning, Leah wakes him up. She tells him that Anna's father and husband called on the phone and used very bad language. She requests Grein to stop his affairs for the sake of their children. She also tells him that their relationship has come to an end. For Leah, love means family and for Grein love is just a game. When he listens to her words of ending the relationship, Grein also gets ready to depart permanently.

Grein goes into the kitchen where his wife Leah is taking breakfast. She offers him the food and requests him to get rid of his affairs and look after the family. She asks him whether he wants to marry Anna. He tells her that he feels suffocated in the house and wants freedom. Anna gives freedom to his bored life. Grein is very well aware of the fact that whatever he is doing is wrong. He has crossed his forty and needs to be homely. But he is trapped by some energy beyond his control. After some time, Anna calls him and asks him to meet her at Grand Central the next day at nine. He gets confused about what to do by that time. He cannot talk with Leah and his children are not interested in any kind of dialogue with him. He suddenly dials the phone to another woman Esther whom he forgot in that hectic schedule. Whenever Grein is in trouble, it is Esther who comes to his rescue. She loves him madly and that madness makes her possessive about him. He tells her that he wants to meet her that night and she readily calls him to her home.

Esther is a noble woman of forty-three who is widowed from a rabbi and does not have a child. She loves him as if he is her only child and her husband. Grein feels her need as if she is a confession box for him and a mother. They quarrel but again get patched up in a very short

time. He reaches her late at night and she is waiting for him. She jumps at him kisses him all over the face. He holds her for some time in his arms and feels her. She is a beautiful woman with an excellent figure. After some time, telephone rings and she goes to attend the call. Grein is tired and wants to sleep. When he is almost asleep, Esther comes angrily towards him and tells him that the whole town is talking about him. She comes to know that Grein is involved with Anna. Esther asks him to marry her and live with her, but he always denies saying he cannot leave Leah. But this time, he has left Leah and his children for the new woman Anna. She asks him whether he is really in love with Anna or it is a physical attraction. Grein does not reply. She gets angry with him and asks Grein to leave her place.

Anna gets ready to meet Grein. She comes to the meeting place at nine where they are supposed to meet; but Grein is not there. She paces back and forth to pass the time but nothing can help. She suspects that Grein will not come. He cheated on her. When she almost gives up the thought of meeting Grein, he puts his hand on her shoulder. They go into a nearby restaurant and order breakfast. He asks her how many men she had in her life. She honestly tells him that three men came into her life and Grein is fourth. Grein is not happy with her confession. He thinks Anna is the woman who enjoyed men and now is with him. When she sees Grein in a sad mood, she asks him to tell her what he feels about her after listening to her affairs. Grein remains silent. She warns him if he has any doubts about her, he can leave her. She wants to go to him chaste at least spiritually. She also tells him that she had come to say goodbye to him permanently but after meeting him, she has changed her decision.

They decide to go to Miami and live there. Anna is aggressive in whatever she wants. She tells Grein that she wants a son from him. They are in a private railway compartment. Grein

tells Anna about Esther and Anna tells him about Yasha. Two people discuss their affairs to come close. Grein speaks well about Esther but Anna says Yasha was a very bad man. Grein used to visit Anna's mother when Anna was a girl. She asks him whether there was any relationship between them as he frequently visited her. He tells her that they kissed sometimes. Anna is shocked to know this and starts weeping. Anna and Grein both enjoyed partners and now they have started a new life thinking everything will go well. Anna later tells him that she does not mind his relationship with her mother. She tells him that she wants him from the bottom of her heart. They reach Miami and board a hotel. One afternoon, Grein and Anna go out in the lobby where they come across Mrs. Katz who knows Anna as Mrs Luria. She recognises Anna and calls her Mrs Luria. Anna gets very annoyed and tells her that she is no more Mrs Luria but Mrs Grein. It is the first incident where Grein feels ashamed of himself being with Anna. Anna and Grein leave the hotel in a hurry and book a room in a crowded hotel. But there too a man named Morris Gombiner comes and Grein unwillingly recognises him. They have been friends for twenty years.

Anna plans to buy a bungalow near the beach. In the meanwhile, Grein receives a call from Leah telling him that their son is going to marry a gentile named Patricia and requests him to come. Grein leaves Anna for some time, thinking he will go there, settle the matter, and get the money he saved to buy the bungalow. Leah welcomes him with a smile. She tells him that since he is gone, she could not concentrate on her business. Her life has become a misery. Leah needs Grein as her husband, he is her support but Grein is far from this realisation. Grein visits Esther whenever possible. He calls Anna and asks her to return to New York. Anna's husband, Stanislaw Luria is frustrated with his life and

wants to go to Sonia, his dead wife. After a few days of staying alone, Luria settles himself in an armchair in his house and takes his final nap.

Grein's son Jack gets married and settles. Anita, his daughter, takes a job and leaves home. Leah remains alone at home with no work to do. She sells her boutique as it was getting difficult for her to manage it. One day, Grein tells Anna that Leah has developed a lump in her breast and needs to be operated. Initially Anna feels sorry for Leah but later she realises that Grein took away her husband Luria and now it is her turn to take revenge. Without taking any consent or informing him, Anna reunites with her first husband Yasha. After some time, Esther gets married to Plotkin. Grein visits Leah in the hospital before her operation but she does not talk to him. His son and daughter are also there but they also don't pay any attention to him. Grein does not know what to do with his life. He has no option but to sell everything possible and surrender himself to God. He realises that he has done great harm to Leah and his children but it is too late to reconcile. Without informing anybody, he goes to Israel, the land of God. He grows beard and starts living the life of an orthodox Jew. In the epilogue, Singer mentions a letter that Grein writes to his friend Morris Gombiner. In this letter, Grein feels repentant for his misdeeds. He says that he always loved Leah and his children but he cannot go to them. His words about family tell what pain he is going through,

“I lived in sin with women to whom I was not married, derided people, drove others to sickness, suffering, death. Yes, I was a murderer, too. I didn't do my killing at once, but little by little. My children both married Gentiles. My daughter chose a German whose brothers were probably Nazis who ordered Jews to dig their own graves. It is only a short step from shaving off your sidelocks and putting on a necktie to breaking God's laws and mingling your seed with

the seed of Amalek. This is not true just in my case. The modern Jew is, and must be, an assimilationist. His road leads to conversion.” (*Shadows on the Hudson*, 546)

Primary Source:

1. *Shadows on the Hudson*. New York: Farras, Strays & Girous, 1998.

Secondary Sources:

1. Buchen, Irving. *Isaac Bashevis Singer and the Eternal Past*. New York Univ. Press, 1968.

2. Day, John. *In Search of Pre-Exilic Israel*, Bloomsbury Publishing, 2005.
3. Ernest, Abel. *Arab Genetic Disorders: A Layman's Guide*, McFarland, 2003, 4.
4. Eriksen T.H. *Social Identity, intergroup conflict, and conflict reduction*, Oxford University Press'. 2001 Spring, 1964. Israel Shenker, “Isaac Bashevis Singer’s Perspective on God and Man.” New York Times 23 October 1986.